

Electric Dipole Moment of *n*-Amylamine and Molecular Interaction

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The apparent dipole-moment values for *n*-Amylamine in benzene as reported in the literature^{1,2} are not in fair agreement (see discussion). We have therefore examined its value, which has been found to be 1.47 D. The use of the method due to Palit³ in preference to other equations to evaluate the orientation polarisation value has been discussed. Our molecular polarisation data indicate that the probability of dipole association is better indicated than the formation of charge-transfer type complex in the solution. Besides, the observed data assist in understanding the applicability of Earp and Glasstone⁴ theory to study the molecular interaction in a binary mixture.

The equations which have been in frequent use to evaluate the orientation polarisation and then to calculate the solution moment value, are due to Hedestrand⁵, Hoecker⁶, Halverstadt and Kumler⁷, LeFevre and Vine⁸. These authors have obtained their result under a few assumptions.

Recently Palit³ has proposed two theoretical methods for the purpose, through the concept of partial specific-polarisation involving no assumption. The approach of Palit³ appears to be very rational and the equations may give a better insight in analysing the error when other methods are employed. In addition, other equations are directly derivable from the method of Palit³ under some simplified conditions.

The present work (which is in progress) has therefore been undertaken

- i) to examine and understand the merits of the equations suggested by Palit³ ;
- ii) and also to examine the applicability of Earp and Glasstone theory used by earlier workers⁹ to study the molecular interaction in a binary mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL

We have determined the electric dipole moment of *n*-Amylamine in benzene at 30° at a frequency of 1 Mc/Sec. The apparatus in use has been supplied by M/s Toshniwal Brothers, New Delhi and is based upon the principle of heterodyne beat method. The

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resulting beat frequency is projected on the screen of a cathode ray tube with a 50 cycles per second horizontal deflector. A Lissajous figure is obtained on the screen. The reading for the capacitance contributed by the specimen liquid is taken at the appearance of a single loop pattern on CRT. The reading leads to the determination of dielectric constant of the liquid. The values of dielectric constant agree within ± 0.001 unit with the literature values¹⁰ while the cell was calibrated with the standard liquids viz., benzene, cyclohexane, carbon-tetrachloride and dioxan. *n*-Amylamine was dried over KOH and was fractionally distilled in quick fit apparatus where there was no possibility for the liquid to be in contact with atmospheric moisture or carbon dioxide. The fraction boiling between 101–102° was used.

Palit³ has suggested the evaluation of specific-orientation polarisation from the relation

$$p_{2\mu} = \left[\frac{3(\epsilon_1 - \eta_1^2)}{d_1(\epsilon_1 + 2)(\eta_1^2 + 2)} \left(1 - \frac{\beta_0}{d_1} + \frac{3\alpha_0}{d_1(\epsilon_1 + 2)^2} - \frac{6\eta_1\gamma_0}{d_1(\eta_1^2 + 2)^2} \right) \right]$$

Where α_0 , β_0 and γ_0 are respectively the concentration-coefficients at infinite dilution of dielectric-constant, density and refractive index. $p_{2\mu}$ when multiplied by the molecular weight of the solute, gives the molecular-orientation polarisation, which is used to determine the dipole moment value from the relation

$$\mu = 0.01281 P_{2\mu} \text{ (orientation polarisation) } \frac{1}{T^{\frac{1}{2}}} \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ esu.}$$

This value has been further compared and confirmed by evaluating the solution moment from $(P_{2\infty} - P_e)$, $P_{2\infty}$ (the solute polarisation at infinite dilution) has been calculated by the method of Halverstadt and Kumler⁷. The constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler have been evaluated by the method of least square. Electronic polarisation P_e is the same as the molecular-refraction for the Sodium *D* line and has been taken from the literature¹¹. Atomic polarisation has not been considered according to the suggestion of Debye¹² viz., the electronic polarisation calculated from Sodium *D* line partly compensates the neglect of atomic polarisation. Since the solutions employed by us were very dilute, therefore, the value of $P_{2\infty}$ and the dipole moment calculated therefrom were considered to be less accurate as compared to the ones calculated by the method of Halverstadt and Kumler⁷, and Palit³. Therefore the literature values^{1,2} have been compared with those obtained by the methods of earlier workers^{7,8}.

TABLE I

$f_2 \times 10^2$	P_{12}	P_2	$f_1 f_2$	P_E	$\left(\frac{c_{12}^{-1}}{\epsilon_{12}^{+2}} \right)^2$
2.8760	27.93	67.68	.02793	+0.11	0.0945
3.7980	28.35	68.80	.36530	+0.19	0.0968
4.6931	28.69	68.01	.04472	+0.20	0.0986
5.5891	29.18	70.12	.05276	+0.35	0.1014
6.4296	29.52	69.69	.06016	+0.38	0.1032

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TABLE 2

$c_1 = 2.2686$	$d_1 = 0.86766$	$\eta_1 = 1.4960$	
$w_2 \times 10^2$	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	η_{12}
3.198	2.3320	0.86274	1.4925
4.219	2.3553	0.86114	1.4910
5.208	2.3736	0.85974	1.4900
6.196	2.4021	0.85816	1.4890
7.121	2.4198	0.85650	1.4880

Values of the constants in the equation of Palit

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 &= 2.2648 & P_{2\mu} \text{ (orientation polarisation)} &= 43.67 \text{ c.c.} \\ \beta_0 &= -0.1537 & \mu &= 1.47 \text{ D.} \\ \gamma_0 &= -0.1117 \end{aligned}$$

Values of the constants in the equation of Halverstadt and Kumler

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= 2.4947 & \epsilon_1 &= 2.2640 & P_{2\infty} &= 72.24 \text{ c.c.} \\ \beta &= 0.23347 & V_1 &= 1.1525 & P_e &= 28.72 \text{ c.c.} \\ & & \mu &= 1.47 \text{ D.} \end{aligned}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Molecular polarization value 43.67 c.c. of *n*-amylamine in benzene at 30° calculated by the equation of Palit³ is in excellent agreement with polarisation value (43.52 c.c.) determined by the method due to Halverstadt and Kumler⁷. However, both the values give the value of solution moment as 1.47 D. The literature values i.e., 1.55 D by Rao¹ and 1.62 D by Krishna and Srivastava², both appear to be higher.

Regarding the molecular interaction in the solution, the applicability of Earp and Glasstone theory has been examined. The graph $\left(\frac{\epsilon_{12}-1}{\epsilon_{12}+2}\right)^2$ Vs. P_{12} (Fig. 1) is linear, showing that no chemical interaction is there. The values of P^E (the excess polarisation) in column 5th (Table 1) being positive, eliminates the possibility of dipole association as well.

Next the graph P^E Vs $f_1 f_2$ (Fig. 2) though linear does not pass through the origin. This does not lead one to think the possibility of the formation of charge-transfer type complex exclusively in the mixture. In the present case, it is observed that the theory does not assist

much to come to a definite conclusion. As such, our polarisation data for solution restrict the applicability of the theory, below the concentration range $0.065 f_2$. Under the circumstances, we have taken the help of P_2-f_2 curve (Fig. 3) to visualise the probable interaction. The curve P_2-f_2 shows a maximum point suggesting the dipole association through weak

hydrogen bonding. In this respect our data do support the conclusion drawn by Krishna and Srivastava².

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